

ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF ROHINGYA SETTLEMENT ON LAND USE, VEGETATION & LAND SURFACE TEMPERATURE AT BHASAN CHAR, BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The Rohingya are a recognized Indo-Aryan ethnic minority that mostly follow Islam and live in Myanmar's Rakhine State, formerly known as Burma. Prior to the massacre of the Rohingya people in 2017, when over 740,000 people fled to Bangladesh, an estimated 1.4 million Rohingya lived in Myanmar. Over 700,000 Rohingya refugees have been compelled to leave Myanmar since 2017 and relocate to Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. For the accommodation of these huge amount of people the government of Bangladesh chose Bhasan char. This study will assess the impacts of this settlement to the char area in respect to the changes in vegetation, growth of buildup areas and the changes in climatic pattern. This study aims to make a comparative analysis of different spectral indices for analyzing the ecological change pattern in terms of vegetation & buildup of the area. GIS, Remote Sensing and Statistical analyses have been utilized for this observation. The opportunity to integrate field parameters with the Rohingya population and other pertinent data can be provided by the Geographical Information System (GIS), which will aid in evaluating the issue and its effects. For this this study will use different indices like NDVI, NDWI, NDBI, LST etc. A few years ago, the area was full of trees and waterbodies but now the land use pattern has been changed. So that it is creating negative climatic impact on that area. As the growth pattern of the buildup area is increasing alarmingly so the temperature of the land is increasing with the decreasing rate of the greenery, because of creating land for buildup area. This study will further help to determine the changes and its impacts to this area and will help to minimize the inverse results.

Keywords

GIS, Land use change, Remote sensing, Bhasan Char, Bangladesh, Vegetation, Buildup; Land cover/land use change, Water body, Planning.

1. Introduction

Human activity and interaction with the environment lead to environmental change. Due to a number of issues, including an environmental exploitation, deforestation, inappropriate land use, expanding population, and anthropogenic activities, it is experiencing a serious challenge. Changes in land-use & land-cover are the primary reasons for climatic change ([Hathway & Sharples, 2012](#)).

The usage of the remote sensing method in relation to environmental issues is common. Furthermore, advancements in Geographic Information Systems (GIS), computer tools that support mapping, spatially referenced spatial analysis, and tabular data, offer a helpful method in the broader context of environmental monitoring ([Kokalj & Oštir, 2007](#)). There are many methods for change detection in remote sensing applications, especially for changes in vegetation, wetland cover, land use, and land cover ([Sun, X., Tan, X., Chen, K., Song, S., Zhu, X., & Hou, D., 2020](#)).

Since temporary housing is frequently constructed close to environmentally sensitive places like Bhasan Char, so that the effect of the forcefully migrated people on the natural and environment resources of the emcee or innkeeper country has emerged as a new concern in the modern world ([Kafy, A. Al, Dey, N. N., Al Rakib, A., Rahaman, Z. A., Nasher, N. M. R., & Bhatt, A., 2021](#)).

Some environmental deterioration is being brought on by it, including deforestation and the depletion of land degradation, firewood, unstable surface water extraction, water contamination etc ([Zhang, 2017](#)). According to several earlier studies, many forms of environmental degradation have been discovered in various parts of the world. For example, the refugee crisis has caused vegetation and land degradation in Sudan, forest depletion in Western Kenya, and deterioration of agricultural land in Syria. In the instance of Bangladesh, a few studies have recently been conducted with the aim of evaluating the environmental deterioration (focused on vegetation) in Bhasan Char as a result of housing refugees ([Sar, N., Chatterjee, S., & Das Adhikari, M., 2015](#)).

Because of this, more research is required to evaluate the changes in vegetation cover, growth in built-up area, and increase in surface temperature throughout entire time of the influx. By analyzing the changes in accumulation, vegetation cover & land surface temperature in Bhasan Char, a refugee-occupied island, between May 2020 and the present, this study seeks to close that gap in the existing literature.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

An island called Bhasan Char, which was created around 20 years ago, is situated about 28 nautical miles from Chittagong, 13 miles from Hatiya, and about 4 miles from the closest island, Sandwip (Banerjee 2020). The “Ashrayan-3 project” is made up of 120 home plots, 120 cyclone centers, solar power systems, water supplies, internal connection highways, mobile phone networks, and a 9-foot-high embankment for food protection. In order to make this Island habitable, this project also includes sufficient health facilities, short-term employment and livelihood options, and formal and informal educational facilities for Rohingya children. The relocation project has been delayed and hampered by a number of obstacles at this location, which is frequently referred to as the mini town. The Island has been described as unsuitable and unsuited for the Rohingya refugees to reside in reports from various media (such as newspapers, TV, or International Non-Governmental Organization (INGO) reports). Following their reported testimonies of Rohingya displaced individuals allegedly being moved without their knowledge or agreement, the United Nations and Amnesty International sought an impartial evaluation of Bhasan Char’s habitability. As a result, this subject requires scientific consideration and inquiry to determine the Island’s sustainability, livability, and durability.

Figure 01: Map of Bhasan Char

2.2 Data

Basic information of this study was using data from multiple-temporal satellites, specifically from Landsat photos of a specific sensor taken in 2017 and 2022. Among these, data for 2017 was gathered ahead of the start of the refugee influx, while data for 2022 was gathered in April of that year, just as the influx was beginning to fill the built-up housing. Despite the fact that the primary objective of this study is to find changes in vegetation cover and buildup area and their effects on land surface temperature between August 2017 and April 2022, the data from the previous year have also been collected to show a comparison between the recent change and historical change. Table 1 presents specifics of the satellite photos.

Table 1: Data Information

Year	Reference Data	Spatial Resolution	Data Source
2017	Landsat 8 OLI	30 meters	earthexplorer.usgs.gov
2022	Landsat 8 OLI	30 meters	earthexplorer.usgs.gov

2.3 Image processing and classification

Unsupervised and supervised classification are the two main techniques used by image analysis for classifying images (Islam & Hassan, 1970). Unsupervised image classification is a technique where the image interpretation software categorizes or groups the pixels in an image based on their reflectance values without the analyst's input. Supervised image classification is a technique where the analyst creates tiny regions on the picture, known as training sites, that represent each desired land cover category (Hathway & Sharples, 2012). When an image analyst is familiar with the topography of a region and has expertise with the spectral characteristics of the cover classes, the delineation of training areas typical of a cover type is most useful. The program is subsequently trained by the picture analyst to detect spectral signatures or values connected to the training locations. The program utilizes these signatures to categorize the remaining pixels after defining the signatures for each land cover group. Post classification's effectiveness in identifying the location, type, and pace of changes has led to its successful implementation in urban environments by several studies (Kafy, A. Al, Dey, N. N., Al Rakib, A., Rahaman, Z. A., Nasher, N. M. R., & Bhatt, A., 2021).

2.3.1 NDVI

The different groups in this study were divided using the Normalized Differential Vegetation Index (NDVI). NDVI has been calculated for every picture throughout this study period using surface reflectance of the Red and Infra-Red bands. NDVI data ranges from -1 to +1, where positive value is representing mangroves at various density levels and negative values representing water. Close to zero values (0.1 to 0.1) often correlate to desolate regions. As a result, negative NDVI values were not considered in this study. Positive NDVI (different years) values are then utilized to characterize the health and stress levels of the mangroves of this study area (Deng, Y., Yan, Y., Xie, Y., Xu, J., Jiang, H., Chen, R., & Tan, R., 2020).

$$NDVI = \frac{pNIR - pRED}{pNIR + pRED}$$

2.3.2 NDBI

There are several indices available for built-up area analysis. Adjusted Difference The most popular indexes for analyzing built-up regions are the Built-up Index (NDBI), Built-up Index (BU), Urban Index (UI), Index-based Built-up Index (IBI), Enhanced Built-up and Bareness Index (EBBI). These many indices each have their unique computation technique and formula. More SWIR than NIR light is reflected by the bare ground and built-up regions. Infrared spectrum reflection is absent from water bodies. NIR reflection is greater than SWIR reflection in the case of a green surface. The Normalize Difference is another. The value of the build-up index ranges from -1 to +1. Higher NDBI values indicate built-up regions, whereas lower values indicate water bodies. Low NDBI value for the vegetation (Jensen, 2009).

$$NDBI = \frac{pNIR - pMIR}{pNIR + pMIR}$$

2.4 LST

At both the local and global dimensions, land surface temperature (LST) is a crucial factor in the surface energy and water balance. LST has been extracted from thermal infrared (TIR) data collected from space using a variety of approaches. The recovery of the LST continues to be difficult because of the poorly presented issue. We examine the state of LST retrieval techniques using satellite TIR data at the moment. We also go through the techniques used to evaluate satellite-derived LST as well as the temporal normalizing techniques for LST generated from satellites (Jensen, 2009).

$$LST = \frac{BT}{[1 + \{(\lambda * \frac{BT}{\rho}) * \ln \epsilon\}]}$$

Where,

LST = Land Surface Temperature

λ = wavelength of emitted radiance in meters

$\rho = h * c / \sigma$ ($1.438 * 10^{-2}$ mK),

σ = Boltzmann constant (1.38 * 10²³ J/K),
 h = Planck's constant (6.626 * 10⁻³⁴ Js),
 c = Speed of light (2.998 * 10 m/s) and
 ϵ = emissivity (ranges between 0.97 and 0.99)

2.5 Accuracy assessment

The accuracy evaluation phase of the image categorization process is the last one. A procedure to evaluate the categorization with actual data or other sources of information is called accuracy evaluation. It enables assessing a file of categorized images (Eastman, 2009). To ground truth each and every pixel of the categorized image is unusual. So, a few reference pixels are produced. On the categorized image are locations called reference pixels. Each reference pixel in the picture corresponds to a particular geographic coordinate. These reference pixels were chosen at random. Two sets of class are present at the randomly chosen positions in the categorized image list. The actual kind of land cover is represented by the first set of class values. The second class, sometimes referred to as reference values. The researcher enters these reference values, which are based on the ground truth data (Dewan & Yamaguchi, 2009).

The map is validated using the Kappa coefficient (K). K is determined by applying the equation.

$$k = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^r x_{ii} - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+} \times x_{+i})}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+} \times x_{+i})}$$

Where,

N = Number or quantity of pixels.

r = number of rows in matrix.

Xii = number of observations in row land column i.

xi+ and x+i are the marginal totals for row and column i, respectively.

Table 2: Accuracy Assessment

Year	Classification Accuracy	Kappa Statistics
2017	89.61%	0.8479
2022	90.79%	0.8757

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Land-use & land-cover change

Absolute variation in hectares [Note: A (+) sign denotes a gain and a (-) sign a reduction in a different time period.

Table 3: LULC Change

Land Use Categories	Changed Area(ha) (2017–2022)
Vacant Land	+1074.21
Sandy Land	-80.71
Vegetation	-3604.58
Water Bodies	-1516.09
Refugee Camp	+2495.63

Here it shows that the vacant land and vegetation lands has been destroyed most in the past few years for constructing the refugee camp in the Bhasan Char.

Figure 2: (a) LULC of 2017 (b) LULC of 2022 (c) Change Detection LULC of Bhasan Char from 2017 to 2022

3.1.2 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

Figure 3: (a) NDVI map 2017

(b) NDVI map 2022

Here the figure 3 shows that the vegetation is significantly change between this five year, the amount of vegetation is decrease in the central area of Bhasan char where mainly the Rohingya settlement grew. The index also shows that the highest value of NDVI is decreases from 0.43 to 0.4.

3.1.3 Normalized Difference Buildup Index (NDBI)

Figure 4: (a) NDBI map 2017

(b) NDBI map 2022

The settlement can be clearly seen in the figure 3(b). In 2017 there are no settlement or any buildup area in Bhasan char but in 2022 significant amount of buildup area grown up, the red marks on in map of 2022 shows the buildup area.

3.1.4 Land Surface Temperature (LST):

Figure 5: (a) LST map 2017

(b) LST map 2022

Due to increase in settlement the land surface temperature is also increase in 2022. The minimum temperature in 2017 was only 29.02^o C but in 2022 it is increased to 30.2^o C. The maximum temperature is also increased from 35.59^o C to 42.6^o C.

3.1.5 Relationship between NDBI & LST:

Figure 6: (a) NDBI vs LST 2017

(b) NDBI vs LST 2022

Figure 6 shows a positive correlation between NDBI and LST. In 2017 the correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.97$ but in 2022 the coefficient is almost reach to 1, here $R^2 = 0.9969$. This demonstrates that the LST values increase with increasing built-up areas.

3.2 Discussion

The Rohingya's were transfer to the Bhasan char in 2020, which can be identify from the NDBI map, in figure 3(b) the center portion of the Bhasan char is show in rad mark which indicate the Buildup area with a NDBI value of 0.07 to 0.17. But in figure 3(a) there is no higher value of NDBI on the center area which mean there were no settlement or buildup area in 2017. The figure 3 shows the distribution of NDVI in 2017 and 2022. The range of NDVI in 2017 is about – 0.26 to 0.43 but in 2022 it is – 0.15 to 0.4 which refers a significantly change in vegetation on the study area. Due to the increase in Buildup area the vegetation is changed. For all this change the surface temperature in this area is also changed (Zhang, Y., Murray, A. T., & Turner, B. L., 2017). The vegetation body had lower temperature as compares to the other areas such as built-up areas. The maximum temperature is changed about 5⁰ to 7⁰ C from 2017 to 2022. In 2017 to 2022 at the central part of the study area NDVI intensity is low due to massive expansion of NDBI. So, the land surface temperature rises. Figure 5(b) shows that the surface temperature is 40.9⁰ to 42.6⁰ C in most of the part of Bhasan Char, but it was only 34.17⁰ to 35.6⁰ C in 2017. So, it can be said that due to Rohingya settlement the surface temperature increases, and vegetation decreases in Bhasan Char.

4. Conclusion

In this study, attempts have been undertaken to investigate how changes in vegetation and built-up areas affect the temperature of the earth's surface. Analysis was done on the relationship between surface temperature and green and non-green regions. The Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS was used to produce the Land Surface Temperature (LST), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI). The two urban factors (built up area and green space) and Land Surface Temperature (LST) were evaluated for their relationship. LST and built-up areas show a positive association with R² = 0.97 and 0.99 for the respective seasons of 2017 and 2022. This illustrates that the LST values increase with the density of built-up regions. It demonstrates how much land surface temperature is produced by populated areas. Furthermore, temperature variations between plant-covered regions and their surrounds suggest that vegetation can lower surface temperatures. The two most significant aberrations that might be a big contributor to a rise in temperature are the rapid growth of built-up areas and loss of plant cover.

So, it can be said that the settlement should be done in a way that it would not hamper the vegetation cover of the area so that the land surface temperature will be able to keep tolerable limit for livelihood.

References

- Amnesty International (2020) Let us speak for our rights: human rights situation of Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh. Amnesty International, London
- Banerjee S (2020) From Cox's Bazar to Bhasan Char: an assessment of Bangladesh's relocation plan for Rohingya refugees. Observer Research Foundation, Dhaka
- Deng, Y., Yan, Y., Xie, Y., Xu, J., Jiang, H., Chen, R., & Tan, R. (2020). Developing shopping and dining walking indices using POIs and remote sensing data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(6), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9060366>
- Dewan, A. M., & Yamaguchi, Y. (2009). Land use and land cover change in Greater Dhaka, Bangladesh: Using remote sensing to promote sustainable urbanization. *Applied Geography*, 29(3), 390–401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2008.12.005>
- EPA. (2012, March). What are Suspended and Bedded Sediments (SABS) in water: WARSSS.
- Geymen, A. and Kucukmehmetoglu, M. Measuring the spatial impacts of urbanization on the surface water resource basins in Istanbul via remote sensing. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 2007.
- Illius S (2019) An inside look at Bhashan Char—the new home for Rohingyas. <https://tbsnews.net/rohin-nya-crisis/inside-look-bhashan-char-new-home-rohingyas>. Accessed 27 Dec 2020
- Hathway, E. A., & Sharples, S. (2012). The interaction of rivers and urban form in mitigating the Urban Heat Island effect: A UK case study. *Building and Environment*, 58, 14–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2012.06.013>
- Hardin, P.J., Jackson, M.W., Otterstorm, S.M., 2007. Mapping, measuring and modelling urban growth. *Geospatial technologies in urban environments, policy, practice and pixels*, second ed. Springer-verlag, Heidelberg, pp. 141-176
- Islam, M. R., & Hassan, M. Z. (1970). Land Use Changing Pattern And Challenges For Agricultural Land: A Study On Rajshahi District. *Journal of Life and Earth Science*, 6(February 2012), 69–74. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jles.v6i0.9724>
- Jensen, J. R. (2009). Remote Sensing of the Environment: An Earth Resource Perspective, 2nd Ed. In *Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ*.
- Kafy, A. Al, Dey, N. N., Al Rakib, A., Rahaman, Z. A., Nasher, N. M. R., & Bhatt, A. (2021). Modeling the

- relationship between land use/land cover and land surface temperature in Dhaka, Bangladesh using CA-ANN algorithm. *Environmental Challenges*, 4(May), 100190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2021.100190>
- Kokalj, Ž., & Oštir, K. (2007). Land cover mapping using Landsat satellite image classification in the classical Karst - Kras region. *Acta Carsologica*, 36(3), 433–440. <https://doi.org/10.3986/ac.v36i3.177>
- Reliefweb (2020) Press Statement: United Nations Statement on the Relocation of Rohingya Refugees to Bhasan Char. <https://reliefweb.int/report/bangladesh/press-statement-united-nations-statement-relocation-rohingya-refugees-bhasan-char>. Accessed 16 Feb 2021
- Sar, N., Chatterjee, S., & Das Adhikari, M. (2015). Integrated remote sensing and GIS based spatial modelling through analytical hierarchy process (AHP) for water logging hazard, vulnerability and risk assessment in Keleghai river basin, India. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 1(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-015-0039-9>
- Shimu, S. A., Aktar, M., Afjal, M. I., Nitu, A. M., Uddin, Md. P., & Al Mamun, Md. (2019). NDVI Based Change Detection in Sundarban Mangrove Forest Using Remote Sensing Data. 2019 4th International Conference on Electrical Information and Communication Technology (EICT), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EICT48899.2019.9068819>
- Sun, X., Tan, X., Chen, K., Song, S., Zhu, X., & Hou, D. (2020). Quantifying landscape-metrics impacts on urban green-spaces and water-bodies cooling effect: The study of Nanjing, China. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 55(August). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126838>
- The Daily Star (2020) 40 Rohingyas reach Bhasan Char to visit accommodation project. <https://www.thedailystar.net/40-rohingya-refugees-their-way-visit-bhasan-char-project-1956293>. Accessed 27 Dec 2020
- Xu, H. (2005): A Study on Information Extraction of Water Body with the Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI). *Journal of Remote Sensing*. 9: 589-595.
- Zhang, Y., Murray, A. T., & Turner, B. L. (2017). Optimizing green space locations to reduce daytime and nighttime urban heat island effects in Phoenix, Arizona. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 165(April), 162–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.04.009>